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REGIONAL AND GRADE-SPECIFIC EVALUATION OF FLUORIDE IN SRI LANKAN BLACK TEA INFUSIONS FROM UVA AND NUWARA ELIYA

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Fluoride (F⁻) levels in black tea are an often-overlooked public health and environmental concern, mainly due to the possibility of cumulative exposure through daily consumption. This study assessed the fluoride content in black tea infusions collected from the Uva and Nuwara Eliya regions of Sri Lanka, with special attention to regional and grade-related differences. F⁻ concentrations of 35 tea samples from Uva (17) and Nuwara Eliya (18) regions were determined using an ion-selective electrode method. The results indicated clear variations between regions and across tea grades. The highest concentration recorded was 2.30 mg/L in Nuwara Eliya (FBOP1 grade), while Uva showed a maximum of 2.02 mg/L (BOPSP grade). The lowest value, 1.41 mg/L, was noted for the OPA grade from Nuwara Eliya. These differences are potentially influenced by environmental and agronomic factors such as soil pH, rainfall, and cultivation intensity typical of high-grown teas. The study also confirmed that finer grades, including FBOP1 and BOPSP, tend to accumulate more F⁻ compared to larger-leaf varieties like OPA. Although the observed levels were below the World Health Organization's guideline of 4.0 mg/L for drinking water, the regular intake of tea, together with other dietary sources of fluoride, may contribute to excessive exposure in sensitive populations. The findings highlight the need for region-specific cultivation and processing strategies, as well as better management of soil conditions, to help reduce F⁻ content and ensure consumer safety.

Keywords: Fluoride, Black tea, Sri Lanka, Tea grade